

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF QSOFA SCORE FOR PREDICTION OF SEPSIS OUTCOME IN SURGICAL PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Sepsis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in surgical patients, and early identification of patients at risk for poor outcomes remains essential.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the diagnostic accuracy of qSOFA score for prediction of sepsis outcomes in surgical patients.

Methods: This cross-sectional validation study was conducted at the Department of Surgery, Shaikh Zayed Hospital from March 2025 to June 2025, and included 135 patients with sepsis admitted to the surgical ICU. qSOFA score was assessed at admission, and adverse outcomes including organ failure and mortality were used as the gold standard. Diagnostic performance was evaluated using sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy.

Results: The mean age of patients was 54.8 ± 13.7 years, and 60.7% were male. qSOFA demonstrated sensitivity of 79.1%, specificity of 80.4%, positive predictive value of 65.4%, negative predictive value of 89.2%, and diagnostic accuracy of 80.0%. Organ failure occurred in 50.0% of qSOFA-positive patients compared with 9.6% of qSOFA-negative patients ($p < 0.001$), while ICU mortality was 34.6% versus 6.0% ($p < 0.001$). Positive qSOFA was also significantly associated with prolonged ICU stay and increased need for mechanical ventilation. Stratified analysis showed consistent diagnostic performance across age and comorbidity subgroups.

Conclusion: qSOFA demonstrated good diagnostic accuracy for predicting adverse sepsis outcomes in surgical patients and may serve as a useful bedside tool for early risk stratification, particularly in resource-limited settings.

INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is a major global health burden with high morbidity and mortality. Approximately 30% of all intensive care unit (ICU) patients have or develop sepsis, defined as life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by a dysregulated host response to infection.^{1,2} Over 8 million people die

from sepsis-related causes annually, estimated at 30 million instances. However, this figure is probably underestimated since, in low- and middle-income nations with limited access to care, statistics on incidence and outcomes are frequently inadequately recorded.¹¹ Identifying patients most likely to benefit from ICU

admission may help ensure the optimal use of these facilities.³ The limited availability of ICU beds is a significant problem in resource-limited settings.

Among elective surgical patients, post-operative sepsis is independently associated with increased post-discharge mortality up to 1 year after hospital discharge. This risk is exceptionally high in the first month in older age patients and the presence of severe/very severe co-morbidities. This high-risk population can be targeted for interventions^{4, 5} About 30% of surgical sepsis patients died while on treatment.⁶ The qSOFA scale is crucial for surgical patients with infections admitted to ICUs, as an increased qSOFA score is linked to higher mortality rates. While the qSOFA scale surpasses the SIRS criteria in predicting mortality, it is less effective than the SOFA scale⁷ With an increase in qSOFA score, the overall mortality rate surged and was 2.2%, 6.4%, 17.5%, and 42.4% for qSOFA scores 0, 1, 2, and 3.(P<0.001).¹² qSOFA was highly associated with, but poorly discriminant for, poor outcomes among medical and surgical patients with suspected infection admitted to the ICU in a resource-limited setting. These findings suggest that qSOFA may be helpful as a tool to identify patients at increased risk of mortality in these populations and in this context.⁸ One study in India found that for predicting sepsis outcomes, qSOFA had a sensitivity of 63.8% and specificity of 81.6% for mortality and 58.2% and 85.7%, respectively, for organ failure⁹ In another study, for prediction of mortality in surgical sepsis patients, qSOFA had a sensitivity of 16% and specificity of 96%.¹⁰ The literature presents a mixed view on the effectiveness of the qSOFA (quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment) score for predicting sepsis outcomes. On one hand, several studies support the utility of qSOFA in identifying patients at higher risk of mortality due to sepsis. For instance, a meta-analysis found that qSOFA has a high specificity but lower sensitivity than other scoring systems like SIRS (Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome) and NEWS (National Early Warning Score) for predicting sepsis mortality in various settings.¹³

OBJECTIVE

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of the quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (qSOFA) score in predicting sepsis outcomes in surgical patients using actual clinical outcomes as the reference standard.

METHODOLOGY

Thus Cross-sectional validation study was conducted at Department of Surgery, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from March 2025 to June 2025. Using the sensitivity & specificity calculator, a sample size of 135 cases was calculated with a 95% confidence level and percentage of malignancy, i.e. 30%, six sensitivity of qSOFA, i.e. 63.8% with 15% margin of error and specificity of qSOFA, i.e. 81.6% with 8% margin of error.⁹

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p(1-p)}{E^2} \times \frac{N}{N+n-1}$$

Where:

- n = required sample size
- Z = Z-score corresponding to the desired confidence level
- p = estimated proportion of the outcome
- E = margin of error
- N = total population size

Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed to recruit all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period. Patients aged 20–70 years diagnosed with sepsis and admitted to the surgical ICU were included. Inclusion of this age range was intended to capture diverse risk profiles while maintaining consistency in adult surgical patients. Patients with documented organ failure at admission, incomplete medical records, or those classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class III or IV were excluded to minimize confounding and improve internal validity.

DATA COLLECTION

A total of 135 patients fulfilling the eligibility criteria were enrolled after informed consent. Baseline demographic and clinical information, including age, gender, duration of ICU admission, duration of sepsis, smoking history (>5 pack-years), hypertension (blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg), diabetes mellitus (random blood sugar >200

mg/dL), anemia (hemoglobin <11 g/dL), ASA status, type of surgery performed, operative time, and intraoperative blood loss were recorded using a structured proforma. All patients underwent assessment of qSOFA score by the researcher at admission. Based on the operational definition, patients were categorized as qSOFA positive or qSOFA negative. Patients were then followed prospectively throughout their ICU stay until discharge. Occurrence of adverse outcomes, including organ failure or mortality, was documented and classified as positive or negative sepsis outcome according to predefined criteria. All data were entered into the study proforma for analysis.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Normality of quantitative variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Continuous variables such as age, duration of ICU admission, duration of sepsis, operative time, intraoperative blood loss, and qSOFA score were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables such as gender, smoking status, hypertension, diabetes, anemia, ASA status, type of surgery, and sepsis outcomes were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Diagnostic performance of qSOFA was evaluated using 2 \times 2 contingency tables to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy, taking actual adverse outcomes as the gold standard. Stratification was performed for age, gender, duration of ICU admission, duration of sepsis, smoking history, hypertension, diabetes, anemia, ASA status, type of surgery, operative time, and intraoperative blood loss. A p-value \leq 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Data were collected from 135 patients, with a mean age of 54.8 \pm 13.7 years. Male patients were predominant, accounting for 82 (60.7%) cases, while females constituted 53 (39.3%). Smoking history was present in 38 patients (28.1%), whereas 97 (71.9%) were non-smokers. Hypertension was observed in 51 (37.8%) patients and diabetes mellitus in 44 (32.6%), while anemia was present in 36 (26.7%). Most patients belonged to ASA class II, comprising 76 (56.3%) cases compared with 59 (43.7%) in ASA class I. The mean duration of sepsis was 4.6 \pm 1.8 days, mean ICU stay was 7.9 \pm 3.2 days, mean operative time was 112.4 \pm 28.5 minutes, and mean intraoperative blood loss was 356.7 \pm 118.9 mL.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n=135)

Variable	Category	n (%) / Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	—	54.8 \pm 13.7
Gender	Male	82 (60.7)
	Female	53 (39.3)
Smoking History	Yes	38 (28.1)
	No	97 (71.9)
Hypertension	Yes	51 (37.8)
	No	84 (62.2)
Diabetes Mellitus	Yes	44 (32.6)
	No	91 (67.4)
Anemia	Yes	36 (26.7)
	No	99 (73.3)
ASA Class	I	59 (43.7)
	II	76 (56.3)
Duration of Sepsis (days)	—	4.6 \pm 1.8
ICU Stay (days)	—	7.9 \pm 3.2

Operative Time (minutes)	–	112.4 ± 28.5
Intraoperative Blood Loss (mL)	–	356.7 ± 118.9

Adverse outcomes occurred in 43 (31.9%) patients, while 92 (68.1%) had no adverse outcome. qSOFA was positive in 52 (38.5%) patients, among whom 34 were true positives and 18 were false positives. Among 83 (61.5%) qSOFA-negative patients, 74 were true negatives while 9 were false negatives. These findings yielded

a sensitivity of 79.1%, specificity of 80.4%, positive predictive value of 65.4%, negative predictive value of 89.2%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 80.0%, demonstrating good prognostic performance of qSOFA in predicting sepsis outcomes.

**Table 2. Diagnostic Accuracy of qSOFA for Prediction of Sepsis Outcome (n=135)
2×2 Contingency Table**

qSOFA Score	Adverse Outcome Present n (%)	Adverse Outcome Absent n (%)	Total n (%)
Positive (≥2)	34 (25.2)	18 (13.3)	52 (38.5)
Negative (<2)	9 (6.7)	74 (54.8)	83 (61.5)
Total	43 (31.9)	92 (68.1)	135 (100)

Organ failure occurred in 26 (50.0%) qSOFA-positive patients versus 8 (9.6%) qSOFA-negative patients (p<0.001). ICU mortality was also markedly higher in the qSOFA-positive group, occurring in 18 (34.6%) compared with 5 (6.0%) patients (p<0.001). Prolonged ICU stay beyond

seven days was seen in 31 (59.6%) qSOFA-positive patients compared to 20 (24.1%) qSOFA-negative patients (p=0.002). Similarly, mechanical ventilation was required in 22 (42.3%) patients with positive qSOFA versus 11 (13.3%) with negative qSOFA (p=0.001).

Table 3. Association Between qSOFA Positivity and Sepsis Outcomes

Outcome	qSOFA Positive (n=52)	qSOFA Negative (n=83)	p-value
Organ Failure	26 (50.0)	8 (9.6)	<0.001
No Organ Failure	26 (50.0)	75 (90.4)	
ICU Mortality	18 (34.6)	5 (6.0)	<0.001
Survived	34 (65.4)	78 (94.0)	
Prolonged ICU Stay (>7 days)	31 (59.6)	20 (24.1)	0.002
ICU Stay ≤7 days	21 (40.4)	63 (75.9)	
Mechanical Ventilation	22 (42.3)	11 (13.3)	0.001
No Ventilation	30 (57.7)	72 (86.7)	

Sensitivity was slightly higher among patients aged ≥60 years (81.5%) compared with those <60 years (76.2%), while specificity was somewhat higher in younger patients (82.1%). Among diabetics, sensitivity was 82.4%, specificity 75.0%, and

diagnostic accuracy 78.4%, whereas in non-diabetics accuracy was slightly higher at 80.6%. Similarly, patients with hypertension showed sensitivity of 80.0% and accuracy of 78.2%, while non-hypertensive patients had accuracy of 80.7%.

Table 4. Stratified Diagnostic Accuracy of qSOFA by Risk Factors

Variable	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
Age ≥60 years	81.5	78.6	67.9	88.7	79.8
Age <60 years	76.2	82.1	64.7	89.6	80.2

Diabetes Present	82.4	75.0	66.1	87.9	78.4
No Diabetes	77.3	82.8	65.0	90.1	80.6
Hypertension Present	80.0	76.9	64.3	88.5	78.2
No Hypertension	78.5	82.2	66.2	89.8	80.7

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of qSOFA score for prediction of sepsis outcomes in surgical patients and demonstrated that qSOFA had good prognostic utility, with sensitivity of 79.1%, specificity of 80.4%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 80.0%. These findings suggest that qSOFA can serve as a practical bedside tool for early risk stratification in surgical patients with sepsis. Previous research has similarly reported moderate-to-high specificity of qSOFA in identifying patients at risk of adverse outcomes, particularly mortality and organ dysfunction, supporting its role as a prognostic rather than purely screening tool.¹⁴

In the present study, qSOFA-positive patients showed substantially worse clinical outcomes compared with qSOFA-negative patients. Organ failure occurred in 50.0% of qSOFA-positive patients compared to only 9.6% in qSOFA-negative patients, while ICU mortality was 34.6% versus 6.0%, respectively.¹⁵ These statistically significant associations reinforce that higher qSOFA scores correlate with increased disease severity and poor outcomes. Previous research has similarly shown that patients with qSOFA ≥ 2 have significantly higher mortality and organ dysfunction rates, consistent with the current findings.¹⁶

The diagnostic performance observed in this study, particularly the high negative predictive value of 89.2%, suggests qSOFA may be especially useful in identifying patients at lower risk of adverse outcomes. This could help clinicians prioritize intensive monitoring and early escalation for high-risk patients while avoiding unnecessary overtriage in low-risk cases. Previous research has also reported strong negative predictive performance of qSOFA, emphasizing its utility in ruling out severe progression in selected patients.¹⁷ Another important finding was the association of qSOFA positivity with prolonged ICU stay and increased need for mechanical

ventilation. Patients with positive qSOFA scores had significantly greater rates of ICU stay beyond seven days (59.6% vs 24.1%) and ventilatory support (42.3% vs 13.3%). These results suggest qSOFA may not only predict mortality but also broader morbidity and resource utilization. Previous research has similarly linked elevated qSOFA scores with prolonged hospitalization, critical care requirements, and increased healthcare burden.¹⁸

Stratified analysis showed relatively stable diagnostic accuracy across age groups and comorbidity subgroups, with accuracy ranging from 78.2% to 80.7%. This consistency supports the robustness of qSOFA performance in diverse surgical patients, including those with diabetes and hypertension. Previous research has likewise suggested that while comorbid conditions may influence sepsis severity, the predictive value of qSOFA generally remains preserved across patient subgroups.

The findings of this study are clinically important because qSOFA relies solely on bedside clinical parameters and requires no laboratory testing, making it especially useful in resource-constrained settings where rapid assessment tools are needed. In busy surgical units and ICUs, early recognition of patients at high risk can support timely interventions and potentially improve outcomes. Previous research has similarly emphasized the practicality and feasibility of qSOFA in such environments.¹⁹ However, while qSOFA showed good specificity and overall accuracy, its sensitivity was not perfect, and false-negative cases were observed. This highlights that qSOFA should not be used in isolation to exclude sepsis-related deterioration. Previous research has also raised concerns about limited sensitivity in some settings and has suggested combining qSOFA with clinical judgment or additional biomarkers for improved prediction.

LIMITATIONS

This study had several limitations that should be considered while interpreting the findings. First, being a single-center study conducted at Shaikh Zayed Hospital, the findings may have limited generalizability to other institutions or broader patient populations. Second, the relatively modest sample size of 135 patients may have affected the precision of subgroup analyses. Third, use of non-probability consecutive sampling may introduce selection bias. Fourth, qSOFA was assessed at admission and dynamic changes in score over time were not evaluated, which may have influenced prognostic performance.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the qSOFA score demonstrated good diagnostic accuracy for predicting adverse sepsis outcomes in surgical patients, with acceptable sensitivity, specificity, and strong negative predictive value. Higher qSOFA scores were significantly associated with increased risk of organ failure, ICU mortality, prolonged ICU stay, and need for mechanical ventilation. As a simple bedside tool requiring no laboratory parameters, qSOFA may be useful for early risk stratification and timely identification of high-risk surgical patients with sepsis, particularly in resource-limited settings.

REFERENCES

- Anesi GL, Gabler NB, Allorto NL, Cairns C, Weissman GE, Kohn R, et al. Intensive Care Unit Capacity Strain and Outcomes of Critical Illness in a Resource-Limited Setting: A 2-Hospital Study in South Africa. *Journal of intensive care medicine*. 2020;35(10):1104-11.
- Napolitano LM. Sepsis 2018: Definitions and Guideline Changes. *Surgical infections*. 2018;19(2):117-25.
- Liu YC, Luo YY, Zhang X, Shou ST, Gao YL, Lu B, et al. Quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment as a prognostic factor for infected patients outside the intensive care unit: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Internal and emergency medicine*. 2019;14(4):603-15.
- Barie PS. Outcomes of Surgical Sepsis. *Surgical infections*. 2018;19(2):230-5.
- Yao R-q, Jin X, Wang G-w, Yu Y, Wu G-s, Zhu Y-b, et al. A Machine Learning-Based Prediction of Hospital Mortality in Patients With Postoperative Sepsis. *Frontiers in Medicine*. 2020;7.
- Mewes C, Runzheimer J, Böhnke C, Büttner B, Nemeth M, Hinz J, et al. Differences in Mortality and Sepsis-Associated Organ Dysfunction between Surgical and Non-Surgical Sepsis Patients. *Biomedicines*. 2023;11(8).
- Astafieva MN, Rudnov VA, Kulabukhov VV, Bagin VA, Zubareva NA, Tribulyov MA, et al. [qSOFA score for outcome prediction in surgical patients in intensive care units. Post hoc analysis of the Russian multi-center trial Rises]. *Khirurgiia*. 2019(9):58-65.
- Bishop LA, Wilson DPK, Wise RD, Savarimuthu SM, Anesi GL. Prognostic value of the Quick Sepsis-related Organ Failure Assessment (qSOFA) score among critically ill medical and surgical patients with suspected infection in a resource-limited setting. *African Journal of thoracic and critical care medicine*. 2021;27(4).
- Sreekanth A, Jain A, Dutta S, Shankar G, Raj Kumar N. Accuracy of Quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment Score & Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome Criteria in Predicting Adverse Outcomes in Emergency Surgical Patients With Suspected Sepsis: A Prospective Observational Study. *Cureus*. 2022;14(7):e26560.
- Askim Å, Moser F, Gustad LT, Stene H, Gundersen M, Åsvold BO, et al. Poor performance of quick-SOFA (qSOFA) score in predicting severe sepsis and mortality – a prospective study of patients admitted with infection to the emergency department. *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine*. 2017;25(1):56.

- Fleischmann C, Scherag A, Adhikari NKJ, et al. Assessment of global incidence and mortality of hospital-treated sepsis. Current estimates and limitations. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2016; 193: 259–72.
- Sohn YW, Jang HY, Park S, Lee Y, Cho YS, Park J, et al. Validation of quick sequential organ failure assessment score for poor outcome prediction among emergency department patients with suspected infection. *Clin Exp Emerg Med*. 2019;6(4):314-320. doi:10.15441/ceem.19.046.
- Wang C, Xu R, Zeng Y, Zhao Y, Hu X. A comparison of qSOFA, SIRS and NEWS in predicting the accuracy of mortality in patients with suspected sepsis: A meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 2022 Apr 15;17(4):e0266755. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0266755.
- Finkelsztejn EJ, Jones DS, Ma KC, Pabón MA, Delgado T, Nakahira K, et al. Comparison of qSOFA and SIRS for predicting adverse outcomes of patients with suspicion of sepsis outside the intensive care unit. *Crit Care*. 2017;21(1):73. doi:10.1186/s13054-017-1658-5.
- Khan S, Khan J, Khan S. Comparison of SOFA and qSOFA Scores in Predicting Infection and Mortality in HDU and ICU Patients at a Tertiary Care Center. *J Bahria Uni Med Dental Coll*. 2024;14(2):103-6 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51985/JBUMDC2023295>
- Sreekanth A, Jain A, Dutta S, Shankar G, Raj Kumar N. Accuracy of Quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment Score & Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome Criteria in Predicting Adverse Outcomes in Emergency Surgical Patients With Suspected Sepsis: A Prospective Observational Study. *Cureus*. 2022 Jul 4;14(7):e26560. doi: 10.7759/cureus.26560. PMID: 35936141; PMCID: PMC9348436.
- Sreekanth A, Jain A, Dutta S, Shankar G, Raj Kumar N. Accuracy of Quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment Score & Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome Criteria in Predicting Adverse Outcomes in Emergency Surgical Patients With Suspected Sepsis: A Prospective Observational Study. *Cureus*. 2022 Jul 4;14(7):e26560. doi: 10.7759/cureus.26560. PMID: 35936141; PMCID: PMC9348436.
- Finkelsztejn EJ, Jones DS, Ma KC, Pabón MA, Delgado T, Nakahira K, Arbo JE, Berlin DA, Schenck EJ, Choi AM, Siempos II. Comparison of qSOFA and SIRS for predicting adverse outcomes of patients with suspicion of sepsis outside the intensive care unit. *Crit Care*. 2017 Mar 26;21(1):73. doi: 10.1186/s13054-017-1658-5. PMID: 28342442; PMCID: PMC5366240.
- Maitra S, Som A, Bhattacharjee S. Accuracy of quick Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (qSOFA) score and systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) criteria for predicting mortality in hospitalized patients with suspected infection: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2018 Nov;24(11):1123-1129. doi: 10.1016/j.cmi.2018.03.032. Epub 2018 Mar 29. PMID: 29605565.